

Revolutionising Industry 5.0: unlocking AI-at-the-Edge for sustainable manufacturing transformation

Artificial intelligence (AI) is increasingly becoming a cornerstone of modern technological advancement, profoundly reshaping industries, economies and societies.

In the context of manufacturing, AI's transformative potential is particularly significant as it enables increased efficiency, innovation and competitiveness. AI REDGIO 5.0 is an EU-funded project that exemplifies this transformation by focusing on the integration of AI-at-the-Edge technologies in Industry 5.0 manufacturing for small and medium-sized enterprises (SMEs). This initiative not only aims to revolutionise manufacturing processes but also seeks to build upon the success of previous projects, fostering a new era of digital transformation.

AI REDGIO 5.0 is built upon the ICT Innovation for Manufacturing SMEs (I4MS) programme under Horizon 2020, specifically its Phase IV, which emphasised Digital Innovation Hubs (DIHs) and advanced technologies like AI and digital twins. The I4MS project AI REGIO (Regions and Digital Innovation Hubs alliance for AI-driven digital transformation of European Manufacturing SMEs) developed an Innovation Action which established a synergistic partnership among regions, DIHs, AI solution providers and manufacturing SMEs, introducing innovative methodologies for DIH service portfolios, an AI4EU-focused toolkit of data and AI resources, and a network of Didactic Factories and their Technology and Regulatory Sandboxes

(TERESA). This collaboration fostered an ecosystem of SME-driven experiments and digital transformation pathways. The AI REGIO project played an instrumental role in adopting AI in the manufacturing sector, involving 36 partners from 12 countries and over 20 SME experiments focused on AI-driven transformations to build the factories of the future.

Building on these accomplishments, AI REDGIO 5.0 aligns its efforts with the evolving landscape of Industry 5.0 by transitioning from cloud AI technologies to AI-at-the-Edge, moving from Horizon 2020 to Horizon Europe, and integrating with Digital Europe programmes such as European Digital Innovation Hubs (EDIHs), Data Spaces, and AI Testing and Experimentation Facilities (TEFs) for manufacturing. This alignment ensures that AI REDGIO 5.0 remains at the forefront of technological advancements and global competitiveness.

AI REDGIO 5.0 enhances and expands the H2020 I4MS - AI REGIO partnership, bridging two pilots of the Vanguard Initiative: "Efficient and Sustainable Manufacturing ESM" and the "AI" Pilot. The initiative will involve an increasing number of EU regions and DIHs, facilitating the adoption of competitive AI-at-the-Edge solutions in Industry 5.0 manufacturing SMEs, ensuring they remain competitive and forward-looking.

The project is driven by two distinct types of experiments: SME-driven experiments and didactic factory experiments. The SME-driven experiments demonstrate the development and implementation of AI-based solutions within real industrial settings. Meanwhile, the didactic factory experiments focus on TERESA, incorporating innovative AI applications, tools and services to improve human-machine interaction.

AI REDGIO 5.0's overarching goals are to enable the evolution of manufacturing SMEs towards Industry 5.0, advance cloud AI technologies to AI-at-the-Edge procedures, and adapt the H2020 programme to the requirements of the Horizon Europe and Digital Europe programmes. To achieve these objectives, AI REDGIO 5.0 builds on the outcomes of the H2020 I4MS AI REGIO programme, implementing competitive AI-at-the-Edge digital transformation for SMEs. AI REDGIO 5.0 maintains the momentum of AI technology adoption in manufacturing SMEs while bringing in-depth and breakthrough changes. Key aspects include:

- developing a conceptual framework and reference architecture for AI-at-the-Edge Industry 5.0 applications and experiments
- creating a secure and trustworthy edge-to-cloud continuum of data and computational space for highly distributed AI applications
- ensuring interoperability by design with the pan-EU AI-on-Demand platform and its ecosystem of H2020 and Horizon Europe innovation actions
- transitioning from regional DIHs to a network of EDIHs
- conducting test-before-invest experiments in AI Didactic Factories and TEFs for SME-driven applications
- and supporting the transition towards sustainability through ecosystem development and replication to SMEs.

The project lowers complexity and cost barriers for manufacturing SMEs, enabling them to develop, deploy and fully leverage the cloud/edge computing paradigm for applications like predictive maintenance, quality management, zero defect manufacturing, lifecycle assessment,

intelligent asset management, human-robot collaboration and digital twins. AI REDGIO 5.0 provides free, open-source, user-friendly tools for developing end-to-end pipelines for edge machine learning/AI applications and cloud/edge AI deployment patterns and blueprints for various manufacturing applications.

During the project implementation, seven SMEs will be monitored and supported in their experiments' deployment, and fourteen Didactic Factories across Europe will be involved in didactic experiments for SMEs. Each experiment follows a detailed concept, timeline, milestones, deliverables and expected results, with two iterations for development and refinement. In the medium-to-long term, AI REDGIO 5.0 aims to lower barriers for Industry 5.0 stakeholders by increasing digitalisation and automation in manufacturing, enabling sustainable processes through AI-powered cyber-physical systems. The project democratises AI-based automation, boosts sustainability performance and fosters digitalised flexible value chains through standardised data spaces and interoperable digital twins. Additionally, AI REDGIO 5.0 enhances job attractiveness and safety by improving human-AI collaboration, identifying new skills and job roles essential for the Industry 5.0 workforce, and creating safer, more efficient work environments.

The AI REDGIO 5.0 second open call is now open: a new opportunity for SMEs

The AI REDGIO 5.0 project aims to foster innovation and digital transformation in the manufacturing sector by offering financial support for SME-driven experiments. The project is structured around two waves of open calls to attract third-party participation, providing an opportunity for manufacturing SMEs and small mid-caps to engage in the implementation of cutting-edge AI-at-the-Edge and Industry 5.0 systems. These open calls aim to extend the project's reach and directly benefit SMEs by supporting the incorporation of new experiments that can enhance existing solutions, products or processes.

The selection process for financial support through these open calls focuses on activities that align with the project's broader goals, which include accelerating the adoption of AI technologies and digital transformation in manufacturing. By participating in these open calls, third parties gain complementary funding to fully implement their experiments, contributing to the continued development of AI REDGIO 5.0's ecosystem.

The first open call for the AI REDGIO 5.0 project was launched on 1 December 2023 and closed on 1 March 2024. Since then, the execution phase of the selected experiments has been underway, driving forward the project's goal of integrating AI technologies in real-world manufacturing environments. Currently, the project is live with its second open call, which was launched on 27 September 2024 and will close on 16 December 2024 at 12:00 CET. This call aims to select up to 10 SME-driven experiments focused on implementing AI-at-the-Edge and Industry 5.0 systems. These experiments will further enhance existing solutions, products or processes in the manufacturing sector, directly benefiting SMEs and small mid-caps. Results of the second open call will be communicated from 17 February 2025 to 28 February 2025, and the execution of selected experiments will take place from 31 March 2025 to 30 September 2025. This call is specifically addressed to manufacturing SMEs that are eligible for Horizon Europe funding, providing them with a unique opportunity to participate in the project's transformative journey.

Main topics covered

The AI REDGIO 5.0 project aims to drive digital transformation in manufacturing by leveraging advanced AI technologies, focusing on two key areas: AI-at-the-Edge and Industry 5.0. These areas highlight the convergence of data, AI and IoT technologies, along with the integration of human-centric, sustainable practices in manufacturing processes. By addressing the challenges of modern industry, AI REDGIO 5.0 encourages the development of innovative solutions that enhance

operational efficiency, sustainability and worker well-being.

AI-at-the-Edge—convergence between data and AI continuum, cloud, edge and IoT technologies

AI is profoundly impacting various sectors, and the AI REDGIO 5.0 project focuses on demonstrating its value when implemented at the edge of manufacturing systems. This involves the convergence of cloud and edge computing, providing manufacturing enterprises with benefits such as reduced latency, minimised data transfer, enhanced data sovereignty and improved privacy. AI REDGIO 5.0 invites experiments that explore real-world applications requiring AI and data pipelines at the edge or utilising hybrid cloud-edge infrastructures. These experiments should address challenges related to data quality and design AI pipelines that operate locally in edge computing environments. Potential applications include predictive and prescriptive maintenance, automation, operations planning, waste reduction, energy efficiency and quality control. The use of hybrid architectures for data selection and model accuracy and the deployment of machine learning models on edge systems to optimise manufacturing processes is encouraged. Additionally, the reuse and publication of AI models on the AI-on-Demand platform is strongly recommended to extend the impact of successful solutions.

Industry 5.0—human-centric and sustainable-circular manufacturing, inspired by WISE principles

Industry 5.0 takes the evolution of industrialisation beyond the technical advancements of Industry 4.0 by prioritising human well-being, sustainability, circularity and resilience. It focuses on reintegrating human workers into factories, promoting distributed production, intelligent supply chains and hyper-customisation to ensure a personalised and tailored customer experience.

In this context, AI REDGIO 5.0 encourages experiments that explore how human-centred digitalisation can enhance the flexibility and adaptability of SME production processes, creating more

resilient and sustainable manufacturing systems. The goal is to demonstrate measurable improvements in worker well-being, safer work environments and a reduced environmental impact throughout the product lifecycle.

Proposals should address the integration of AI in circular manufacturing, tackling real-world challenges such as reusability, waste reduction and sustainability. They should also explore human-centric AI tools, like generative models with human-in-the-loop approaches (e.g. large language models), to improve decision-making and the explainability of AI solutions. Applicants are encouraged to use the AI REDGIO 5.0 reference architecture for their solutions, providing realistic business scenarios, key performance indicators and the commitment of SMEs to measure the tangible benefits of their innovations.

Experiments under Topic 2 must address one or more of the following WISE aspects:

- **Well-being, comfort and acceptance**
Examining the impact on mental well-being, self-esteem, frustration, feelings of usefulness, emotional dependence, human dignity, autonomy, oversight and willingness to collaborate with machines.
- **Inclusion and special categories of workers**
Assessing effects on older workers, novices, workers with cognitive or physical disabilities, social isolation and risks of discrimination or bias.
- **Safety of the worker**
Focusing on health and safety, risk of harm and privacy concerns.
- **Ergonomics and improving working conditions**
Analysing impacts on stress and fatigue reduction, and effects on workers' skills.

The second open call for the AI REDGIO 5.0 project offers SMEs a valuable opportunity to integrate these cutting-edge AI technologies into their manufacturing processes. By addressing critical topics like AI-at-the-Edge and sustainable, human-centric manufacturing, the project continues to pave the way for digital transformation and innovation within the manufacturing sector.

PROJECT NAME

AI REDGIO 5.0 - Regions and (E) DIHs alliance for AI-at-the-Edge adoption by European Industry 5.0 Manufacturing SMEs

PROJECT SUMMARY

AI REDGIO 5.0 aims to accelerate the digital transformation of manufacturing SMEs by integrating AI-at-the-Edge and Industry 5.0 systems. The project focuses on developing AI-driven solutions that enhance operational efficiency, sustainability and human-centred practices. Through SME-driven experiments and collaboration across regions, it seeks to foster innovation, improve manufacturing processes and promote a sustainable, resilient industry.

PROJECT PARTNERS

The AI REDGIO 5.0 project involves 44 partners from 18 countries, including Politecnico di Milano as the coordinator. The consortium comprises 22 EU leading-edge regional representatives, 13 EU leading-edge technology providers (including 10 SMEs and mid-caps) and seven industrial case SMEs or mid-caps, all working together to drive digital transformation and AI adoption in manufacturing.

PROJECT LEAD PROFILE

Politecnico di Milano, project lead for AI REDGIO 5.0, is a leading institution in technological research and innovation. With a strong focus on AI, digital transformation and manufacturing, it has contributed to numerous European projects. The university excels in cutting-edge research, industry collaboration and fostering digital ecosystems, aiming to drive technological advancements in various sectors, including Industry 5.0.

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